

Development & Evaluation Study Of Herbal Oral Care Preparation Containing *Vitex Trifolia* & *Coriandrum Sativum*

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ABSTRACT

Polyherbal formulations are pharmaceutical preparations developed by combining different medicinal plants in precise proportions to achieve improved efficacy and better safety profiles. Herbal mouthwashes are formulations prepared from plant-derived substances, used to promote oral health, reduce the risk of dental diseases, and exhibit antimicrobial properties. The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a polyherbal mouthwash containing *Vitex trifolia* and *Coriandrum sativum* and to assess its pharmacognostic, phytochemical, and antimicrobial properties. The plant materials were collected, authenticated, dried, and subjected to solvent extraction. Pharmacognostic evaluations, including organoleptic, physical, and chemical analyses, were performed. The formulated mouthwash was evaluated for parameters such as pH, clarity, stability, and antimicrobial activity against oral pathogens. The results demonstrated that the formulation possessed significant antimicrobial activity and showed acceptable physicochemical characteristics. The study suggests that the developed polyherbal mouthwash can serve as a safe, effective, and natural alternative to conventional synthetic mouthwashes for maintaining oral hygiene..

Keywords: *Vitex trifolia*, *Coriandrum sativum*, polyherbal mouthwash, antimicrobial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Polyherbal formulations involve combining multiple medicinal plants to enhance therapeutic effectiveness and reduce adverse effects [4,21]. These formulations are designed by integrating herbs with complementary or synergistic effects to improve therapeutic outcomes and manage multiple health conditions simultaneously [27]. Such polyherbal approaches have been widely practiced across the world due to their therapeutic and restorative benefits. Herbal mouthwashes are oral hygiene products prepared from natural plant extracts. Compared to synthetic formulations, they offer advantages such as being non-irritating, non-staining, and free from alcohol. Oral diseases such as plaque accumulation, gingivitis, and microbial infections are common global health concerns [22]. Mouth ulcers are painful, shallow lesions that occur on the soft tissues of the oral cavity, including the inner cheeks, lips, tongue, gums, and palate, and are non-contagious. Although

synthetic mouthwashes like chlorhexidine are effective, they are associated with side effects such as tooth staining and altered taste [9,22]. Herbal alternatives provide a promising solution. *Vitex trifolia* (Nirgundi) and *Coriandrum sativum* (Coriander) are well recognized in traditional systems like Ayurveda for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. *Vitex trifolia* (Nirgundi) possesses antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties due to the presence of flavonoids and terpenoids [4,15,23]. *Coriandrum sativum* contains essential oils rich in linalool, which exhibit antimicrobial and biofilm inhibitory activity [2,16]. Therefore, combining these two plants may produce a synergistic effect and provide a safer and effective herbal alternative for oral care [20]. The formulation is optimized in terms of pH, stability, and usability, aiming to provide a safe, effective, and environmentally friendly alternative for oral care.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Types of mouthwash

1. Antiseptic mouthwashes
2. Fluoride mouthwashes
3. Herbal/natural mouthwashes
4. Saline rinse
5. Cosmetic mouthwashes

Advantages

- Can be apply easily
- Economical
- Mouthwashes can reach places in the mouth that brush or floss might miss
- Freshens breath
- Gentle on sensitive mouth

Disadvantages

- It should be used only as an adjunct to mechanical plaque control.
- It does not remain in the mouth for a long time.
- Teeth staining
- Allergic reactions
- Swallowing risk

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Vitex trifolia

Figure 1: *Vitex trifolia* leaves

Taxonomy

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Division: Angiosperms
- Class: Dicotyledonae
- Order: Lamiales
- Family: Lamiaceae
- Genus: *Vitex*
- Species: *Vitex trifolia*

Plant part used: leaves

Chemical Constituents

- Flavonoids (e.g., casticin)
- Iridoid glycosides
- Essential oils
- Diterpenes
- Alkaloids
- Tannins

Uses

- Anti-inflammatory
- Analgesic (pain relief)
- Antimicrobial activity
- Antioxidant

Coriandrum sativum

Figure 2: *Coriandrum sativum* fruits

Taxonomy

- Kingdom: Plantae
- Division: Angiosperms
- Class: Dicotyledonae
- Order: Apiales
- Family: Apiaceae
- Genus: *Coriandrum*
- Species: *Coriandrum sativum*

Plant part used: fruits**Chemical Constituents**

- Essential oils (mainly linalool)
- Terpenes (pinene, limonene)
- Flavonoids
- Coumarins
- Fatty acids
- Proteins and vitamins

Uses

- Antioxidant

- Antimicrobial
- Flavouring agent in food and pharmaceutical preparations

Preparation of plant extract

Aqueous extraction was performed by maceration, a commonly used technique for isolating water-soluble phytoconstituents [35]. Steps involved are;

- The leaves of *Vitex trifolia* and fruits of *Coriandrum sativum* are first washed, air dried, and ground to a powder form to increase the surface area for extraction.
- The powdered plant material is soaked in distilled water, typically for 24–72 hours at room temperature.
- The mixture is stirred or shaken occasionally to promote extraction of compounds.
- After the maceration period, the solution is filtered to separate the plant residue from the aqueous extract.
- The water extract may be concentrated by evaporation over a water bath if needed, yielding a viscous extract for further analysis or use.

Table 1: Formula for herbal mouthwash

SI no.	Ingredients	Quantity		
		Formula 1	Formula 2	Formula 3
1	<i>Vitex trifolia</i>	2 ml	4ml	8ml
2	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	2 ml	4 ml	8 ml
3	Mint oil	0.2 ml	0.4ml	0.6 ml
4	Saccharin	0.1 mg	0.5 mg	0.8 mg
5	PEG	4 g	4.5 g	5 g
6	Glycerol	8.5 ml	8.6 ml	8.7 ml
7	Benzoic acid (10g/100ml)	2 ml	4 ml	5 ml
8	Coloring agent	1-2 drops	2-3 drops	3-4 drops
9	Purified water	Up to 100 ml	Up to 100ml	Up to 100ml

Preparation of herbal mouthwash

Three formulations of herbal mouthwash: Formulation 1(F-1), Formulation 2(F-2), and Formulation 3(F-3) were prepared.

1. Each ingredient was accurately weighed
2. The extract was thoroughly combined with a small amount of water in a mortar and pestle.
3. All of the remaining ingredients were added gradually and thoroughly mixed.
4. Mint oil was added drop by drop and thoroughly combined, taking care to prevent lump formation.
5. Then, drop by drop, PEG 40 and Glycerol were added thoroughly and mixed.
6. Finally, water was added to make the volume, as well as a preservative, and the product was packaged in an attractive, well closed container.

Isolation of mint oil by Clevenger apparatus

The fresh leaves of *Mentha piperita* were hydro-distilled using a glass Clevenger apparatus. A pale greenish yellow essential oil was obtained. It was preserved in the dark at 4°C over anhydrous sodium sulphate drying.

Evaluation of formulated herbal mouthwash

1. Colour

A small quantity of the mouthwash is taken in a clean, transparent glass container and observed visually under daylight against a white background.

2. Odor

The mouthwash sample is smelled gently by wafting air towards the nose.

3. Appearance

The mouthwash is examined visually for clarity, presence of turbidity, precipitation, or opalescence.

4. Texture / Viscosity (Consistency)

A few drops of the mouthwash are rubbed between fingers or tilted in a beaker to assess flow properties. Alternatively, viscosity may be determined using an Ostwald or Brookfield viscometer if available.

5. pH Determination

The pH of the mouthwash is measured using a calibrated digital pH meter or pH paper.

The electrode is immersed in the sample and the pH reading is recorded.

6. Foaming Ability

10 mL of mouthwash is diluted with 10 mL of distilled water in a graduated cylinder. The cylinder is shaken vigorously for a fixed time (e.g., 30 seconds). The height of foam formed is measured immediately.

7. Comparative Evaluation with Reference

All parameters of herbal formulations are compared with the chlorhexidine mouthwash to assess acceptability, stability, and suitability for oral use.

8. Turbidity

Transfer a small quantity of the mouthwash into a clean, transparent glass container. Observe against a white and black background under daylight. Compare with freshly prepared sample or reference

9. Microbial growth

Collect mouthwash sample aseptically and prepare serial dilutions with sterile distilled water. Inoculate on Nutrient agar plates & incubate at 37 °C for 24–48 hrs. Count colonies and express results as CFU/mL.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Phytochemical screening

SI No.	Plant	Alkaloids	Phenolic compounds	Flavanoids	Terpenoids	Essential oil
1	<i>Vitex trifolia</i>	+++	+++	++++	++	++
2	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	++	+++	+++	++	++

Table 3: Evaluation of formulated mouthwash

Parameter	Formula 1	Formula 2	Formula 3	Chlorhexidine Mouthwash (Reference)
Color	Pale yellow	Light amber	Amber	Clear to light yellow
Odor	Mint herbal	Mint herbal (stronger)	Mint herbal(intense)	Medicinal, slightly sweet
Appearance	Clear liquid	Clear liquid	Slightly opalescent	Clear solution
Texture	Smooth, non-viscous	Slightly viscous	Viscous	Non-viscous, watery
pH	5.5 - 6.0	5.8 - 6.2	6.0 -6.5	5.5-6.0
Foaming ability	Low	Moderate	High	Moderate
Turbidity	Absent	Absent	Slightly turbid	Absent
Microbial growth	Absent	Absent	Absent	Absent

Antibacterial Activity of the Extract *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum*

Antibacterial activity of the *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* extracts was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method as per standard microbiological guidelines [37,38]. Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA) plates were inoculated with bacterial suspensions adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard (approximately 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL) by uniform lawn culture using sterile cotton swabs. Wells of 6 mm diameter were aseptically punched into the solidified

agar, and each well was filled with 50 μ L of the respective plant extract (1mg/mL in DMSO), delivering a total of 50 μ L per well. Ciprofloxacin was used as the positive control. DMSO alone served as the negative control. The combination of *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* was also evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours, and the diameter of the inhibition zones was measured using a Zone reader. All experiments were performed in duplicate, and the mean values were recorded to assess the antimicrobial efficacy of each extract.

Table 3: Antibacterial activity of *Vitex trifolia*, *Coriandrum sativum*, Ciprofloxacin, Combination of VT and CS and DMSO against *Staphylococcus aureus*

Compound Code	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (zone of inhibition in mm)
VT	24
CS	24

Ciprofloxacin (5 µg/mL)	36
Blank	0
Combination of VT and CS	34

Figure 3: Zone of inhibition(mm)

Figure 4: Graphical plot of antibacterial activity

Table 4: Stability testing of herbal mouthwash (formulation 2)

Parameter	0 day	7 days	14 days	30 days
Color	Light amber	No change	No change	No change
Odor	Mint herbal(strong)	No change	No change	No change
Appearance	Clear liquid	No change	No change	No change
Viscosity	Slightly viscous	No change	No change	No change
pH	6.0	5.9	5.9	5.8

Foaming ability	Moderate	No change	No change	No change
Turbidity	Absent	No change	No change	No change
Microbial growth	Absent	No change	No change	No change

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate a herbal mouthwash containing *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* as a natural alternative to synthetic mouthwashes. The selected herbal extracts are known for their antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, which are beneficial in maintaining oral hygiene. The formulated mouthwash showed acceptable organoleptic properties, including clarity, pleasant odor, and taste, ensuring good patient compliance. The pH was within the acceptable range for oral formulations, indicating that the formulation is safe for use without causing irritation to oral tissues [22]. Stability studies revealed that the formulation remained physically stable with no significant changes in appearance or consistency. The antibacterial activity of the mouthwash demonstrated effective inhibition of oral pathogenic microorganisms (*Staphylococcus aureus*), which may be attributed to the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and essential oils in both plant extracts [13,15]. The antibacterial activity of the *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* extracts was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* using the agar well diffusion (cup plate) method. The combination of *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* showed improved activity, suggesting a synergistic effect [20]. Compared to synthetic mouthwashes, herbal formulations offer advantages such as reduced side effects and better biocompatibility [9,18]. Hence, the developed herbal mouthwash can be considered a safe, effective, and economical alternative for routine oral care.

CONCLUSION:

The required materials for the herbal mouthwash were collected, dried and authenticated and these materials are powdered. The organoleptic evaluation was done to identify the color, odor, texture, taste etc.

Pharmacognostical studies were carried out like moisture content, ash value, extractive value and physical characters of the powder mixture carried out. Preliminary phytochemical screening was carried out according to standard pharmacognostic procedures [36]. Excipients are added to improve stability and activity of herbal formulation. Excipients like antimicrobial agents, preservative, foaming agent, flavoring agent, coloring agent, sweetening agent were added during the formulation of mouthwash. The antibacterial activity of the *Vitex trifolia* & *Coriandrum sativum* extracts was evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* using the agar well diffusion (cup plate) method. The developed herbal mouthwash containing *Vitex trifolia* and *Coriandrum sativum* demonstrated satisfactory physicochemical stability and significant antimicrobial activity. The combination showed enhanced efficacy, suggesting a synergistic effect between the plant extracts [20]. Thus, the formulation can be considered a safe, effective, and economical alternative to conventional synthetic mouthwashes [18,22]. Based on overall similarity to the reference (chlorhexidine) mouthwash and balanced physicochemical properties, Formula 2 can be considered the best formulation. The stability study of herbal mouthwash (Formulation 2) showed no significant changes in color, odor, appearance, texture, foaming ability, turbidity, or microbial growth over a period of 30 days. Only a slight and acceptable decrease in pH was observed. Hence, Formulation 2 was found to be physically and microbiologically stable and suitable for oral use.

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REFERENCES

1. Puri S, Fatema M, Shewale A, Bele R. Efficacy of herbal mouthwash with extracts of *Coriandrum sativum*, mint and clove in the treatment of chronic gingivitis: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *J Pharm Res Int*. 2021;33(39B):59–63. doi:10.9734/JPRI/2021/v33i39B32180.
2. Kodariah L, Amaliah EY, Fadhillah TI. Antibacterial activity of coriander seeds extract (*Coriandrum sativum*) against *Streptococcus mutans*. *J Indones Med Lab Sci*. 2024;5(2):96–104. doi:10.53699/joimedlabs.v5i2.149.
3. Patel MK, Jain A. *Coriandrum sativum*: review of botany, medicinal uses, pharmacological activities and phytochemistry. *J Drug Deliv Ther*. 2025;15(8):294–302.
4. Gupta MK, Tiwari G, Gupta N, Rajput D. *Vitex trifolia*: a review of ethnobotany and pharmacology. *J Neonatal Surg*. 2025;13(1):1165–1169.
5. *Vitex rotundifolia* L.f. and *Vitex trifolia* L.: review on traditional medicine, phytochemistry and pharmacology. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 2023;289:115064.
6. Antibacterial activity of *Vitex trifolia* essential oil using in vitro and in silico methods. *J Pure Appl Chem Res*. 2023;12(1):26–37.
7. Comparative evaluation of the efficacy of a herbal mouthwash and chlorhexidine on select periodontal pathogens. *J Clin Dent Res*. 2018;12(4):203–210.
8. Comparative assessment of herbal mouthwash with chlorhexidine on plaque accumulation and salivary *Streptococcus mutans*. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2024;16(Suppl 1):S67–S73.
9. Renuka S, Muralidharan NP. Comparison of benefits of herbal and chlorhexidine mouthwashes: a review. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*. 2017;10(2):224–229.
10. Chitsazi M, Shirmohammadi A, Balayi E. Comparison of *Matrica persica* and chlorhexidine. *J Dent Shiraz Univ Med Sci*. 2007;8(2):54–60.
11. Emilson CG, Lindquist B, Wennerholm K. Recolonization of human tooth surfaces by *Streptococcus mutans* after suppression by chlorhexidine. *J Dent Res*. 1987;66(9):1503–1508.
12. Fallahzadeh H, Moeintaghavi A, Foruzanmehr M. Clinical comparison of *Persica* and chlorhexidine mouth rinses: a meta-analysis. *JIDA*. 2006;18:62–70.
13. Mishra B, Singh S, Singh SK. Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial efficacy of *Coriandrum sativum* extracts against oral pathogens. *Int J Pharm Sci Res*. 2019;10(6):2761–2768.
14. Rao PV, Gan SH. Cinnamon: a multifaceted medicinal plant. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 2014;74:101–109.
15. Ahmed A, Khan MR, Rasool N. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activities of *Vitex trifolia* leaves. *Pharmacogn Mag*. 2015;11(Suppl 3):S405–S409.
16. Zhang L, Li X, Zhang H. Antimicrobial activity of coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*) seed essential oil. *J Essent Oil Bear Plants*. 2018;21(6):1538–1546.
17. Prabuseenivasan S, Jayakumar M, Ignacimuthu S. In vitro antibacterial activity of plant essential oils. *BMC Complement Altern Med*. 2006;6:39.
18. Saxena R, Dhiman M, Gupta R. Herbal extracts in oral care products: an overview. *Int J Green Pharm*. 2016;10(4):215–221.
19. Mishra A, Shukla M, Tiwari S. Antioxidant properties of coriander leaf extract. *Food Chem*. 2009;115(3):839–842.
20. Singla R, Garg N, Kaur G. Comparative evaluation of neem and coriander mouth rinses on oral health. *J Dent Med Sci*. 2016;15(10):45–50.

21. Prakash S, Gupta N. Therapeutic uses of Vitex species: a review. *Phytother Res.* 2005;19(9):771–775.
22. Hans M, Kumar V. Evaluation of herbal mouthwash on plaque and gingivitis. *J Indian Soc Periodontol.* 2011;15(4):387–390.
23. Ali M, Houghton PJ. Vitex trifolia and related species: phytochemistry and bioactivities. *Phytochemistry.* 2017;135:18–27.
24. Nayak BS, Sandiford S, Maxwell A. Wound healing activity of coriander extract in rats. *Phytother Res.* 2007;21(4):363–366.
25. Gul K, Gupta A, Singh AK. Nutritional and phytochemical composition of coriander. *J Food Sci Technol.* 2015;52(5):2788–2795.
26. Kaur R, Goyal A, Chauhan A. Evaluation of Vitex trifolia antioxidant activity. *J Herb Med Toxicol.* 2010;4(2):101–107.
27. Farzaei MH, Bahramsoltani R, Rahimi R. Medicinal plants in prevention of periodontal diseases. *Int J Dent Hyg.* 2018;16(1):9–23.
28. Silva NCC, Fernandes A Jr. Biological properties of medicinal plants. *Evid Based Complement Altern Med.* 2011;2011:1–10.
29. Srinivasan D. Coriander: a potential functional food. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr.* 2016;56(4):584–593.
30. Bashir S, Chohan SN. Phytochemical screening of Vitex trifolia. *J Med Plants Res.* 2012;6(11):2313–2317.
31. Singh S, Kumar R. Antibacterial efficacy of herbal mouth rinses. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2015;8(4):205–208.
32. Rajput MS, Kumar A. Formulation of herbal mouthwash with coriander. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2014;76(2):135–140.
33. Javed S, Ahmed N. Comparative study of herbal and chlorhexidine mouthwashes. *J Oral Health Community Dent.* 2018;12(1):20–24.
34. Gupta AK, Tandon N. Indian medicinal plants with antibacterial properties in dentistry. *Indian J Dent Res.* 2004;15(Suppl 1):71–78.
35. Morse DR, et al. Herbal agents in periodontal therapy: a systematic review. *J Periodontol.* 2010;81(5):709–719.
36. Khandelwal KR. *Practical Pharmacognosy: Techniques and Experiments.* Pune: Nirali Prakashan; 2008.
37. Harborne JB. *Phytochemical Methods.* 3rd ed. London: Chapman & Hall; 1998.
38. OECD. *Guidelines for testing of chemicals.* Paris: OECD Publishing; 2001.
39. CLSI. *Performance standards for antimicrobial susceptibility tests.* 12th ed. Wayne (PA): CLSI; 2015.
40. Khare CP. *Indian Medicinal Plants: An Illustrated Dictionary.* New Delhi: Springer; 2007.
41. World Health Organization. *WHO monographs on selected medicinal plants.* Vol. 2. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2002.
42. Nadkarni KM. *Indian Materia Medica.* Vol. 1. Mumbai: Popular Prakashan; 2009.
43. United States Department of Agriculture. *USDA Plants Database.* Available from: <https://plants.usda.gov>.

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